

MESS 0012

The Aether Flexion Wave in Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis (CRH)

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Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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ABSTRACT

The Aether is yet to be understood, anatomically. This is the same issue as Counterspace. However, the author feels there is sufficient evidence to begin looking for flexion waves, perhaps *scalar* waves through the Aether medium by searching for specific quantum fluctuations and disturbances in the atomic mass-energy (ME) spectrum, as well as macrotic behaviors like molecular (and organic) chemistry, HEP plasma, and VLF signal spectrums. Simple metallics that are highly conductive of the PEMF (Force) and probably Aether, and resistive to the Counterspace, may be useful in this endeavor. Crystals, as well as DNA may also provide useful loci/foci to search for these ripples.

Keywords: aether - void - zero point - wave - particle - light - turbulence - plasma - electromagnetism

Wave Behavior in Plasma-Electromagnetic Universe

Many things can be described using wave behavior. It is presumed that the following discovered items can also be modeled using hydrodynamics and wave mechanics:

- The Aether - confirmed with vertical interferometer tests¹ in 2020-2021
- The Counterspace² (aka 0-point, or vacuum energy, or Void) - confirmed in 2022 with Schwinger Effect³
- The neutrino cosmic ray connections to novae⁴
- The baryonic “soup” or “sea of charge” aka cosmic dust
- Condensed matter⁵ crystal plasmas⁶, (liquid metallic hydrogen)
- The Birkeland Current web⁷ (measured as rippling by MMS satellite⁸)

Figure 1 - New Magnetic Process in turbulent Space; credit: NASA⁹

It is also quite possible that the proposed dæther - as discussed previously¹⁰ - can be modeled as a gaseous [numerical] plasma. Mostly for the purposes of creating a double-layer economy¹¹ to surpass our current frail, tension-based economic design, but for other mimsical analyses as well (such as number theories).

What is an AFW?

In the Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis¹², we look for means of moving/pushing/pulling material. One of the main means is the rippling of the magnetic fields, causing motion of charged material, resulting in the

¹ <https://disk.yandex.ru/i/FnUkHxwI5C5EIq>

² https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing_

³ <https://engnews.g7tamil.in/scientists-claim-to-create-matter-from-nothing-prove-schwinger-effect-correct/>

⁴ [Prof. Meyl: Free Neutrino Energy in the whole Universe](#)

⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/condensed-matter>

⁶ <https://vixra.org/abs/1310.0119>

⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1907.06802.pdf>

⁸ <https://youtu.be/LXl2E0-1XXw>

⁹ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/nasa-spacecraft-discovers-new-magnetic-process-in-turbulent-space>

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

¹¹

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPE_MC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

¹² https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

rearrangement of charged electric fields, which results in new arrangements of magnetic fields, etc. There is no start, or stop, it is a consistent rippling caused on the microscopic level by the introduction (at Planck Lengths) of wavelets of (d)ætheric electron-volts we call *quanta*. These are the Quantum Foam¹³, which then combines and forms subatomic particles, particles, atoms, molecules, etc. As the scale increases the vibration rate slows, and inertia increases. The inertia is caused by an impedance value inherent to the RLC characteristic of the interaction of charged (formed) material and the Aether it “floats” in, receiving quantized energy wavelets. The atomized material also exchanges “photonic” packets of circuits¹⁴ that can behave as waves and be modeled as particles, from atom to atom in a vast signals communication sea, we call the electromagnetic spectrum. This spectrum runs from “just above” the Absolute Zero¹⁵ to “infinity”, but we only physically see the visible spectrum of color, and deem this the “middle”. It is only middle relative to us (humans), just as “ground” is only 0 V relative to the Earth.

Now, as the Universe, and its constituent parts, rearrange they disturb the Aether, and presumably the anatomy of the Unknown SCS¹⁶, causing different-sized waves. These will be intrinsically similar to ripples in the electric and magnetic fields of the Sun (and its solar wind) and the Earth.

The AFW, therefore, is nothing more than the motion through this Aether, with the appearance of distinct affectations on the physical atomic realm, which will appear as:

- ❖ Compressions
- ❖ Dilutions (expansions in the field)
- ❖ Contractions
- ❖ Fibrillations (turbulence)
- ❖ Disturbances of amplitude or strength

The purpose of this paper is not to discuss Change Theory, particularly how that relates to the CRH. But it is to discuss how the following simulation, of a laser pulse in a compact electron accelerator, which

displays the 2D version of the 3D Dougherty Set, reflects a greater intrinsic *potential* reality.

Figure 2 - “An image from a simulation in which a laser pulse (red) drives a plasma wave; credit: Genkina/UMD/phys.org¹⁷”

If you’ve ever wondered why something suddenly collapsed, or fell off of a smooth, flat surface, or why anything decayed faster than it should or on average, or why a day slowed or sped up part way through... it might be the

¹³ [YouTube: What is Quantum Foam?- Science at NASA](#)

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

¹⁵ Where $f=0$; <https://www.britannica.com/science/absolute-zero>

¹⁶ Spongy Counterspace - absorbs our energy and entropy and turns it to order in the Hundun (CHAOS)

¹⁷

https://phys.org/news/2022-09-compact-electron.html?fbclid=IwAR1G1se0R8TURHHDREw1NP8weXMJXx1WES9APyArBw_TDCfHXWH2TZQZ71g

effect of an AFW moving through the material Universe, interacting with the atomic realm, subtly. In fact, this may explain most of the non-conscious related *A* power¹⁸ activity that is described as “Heaven” or “spirit world” having effects on the physical world (anecdotally). We’ve already shown that ghost “orbs” are plasmoid in nature¹⁹, rotating on (presumed) Birkeland current spirals. However, what if many ‘miracles’ are simply AFW ripples affecting the material world, with or without consciousness behind them? If it is not a subjective reality only, it is worth \$\$\$\$quadrillions in Change Theory funding to figure it out thoroughly. The dæthereal value alone is in the hundreds of \$\$\$BUSD, if not trillions.

Figure 3 - Vortices pictures as interactions of a traveling wave with the plane ([gif](#)); credit: docsity²⁰

In the above figure all of the aforementioned features appear, and there are hints of rotational spirality as well, thus providing a mechanism for the æthereal mechanics (Weber-Distinti-SAM-Thornhill) and the fractal geometries (of many), in the Laws of Rotation, Relativity, and Resonance. The author makes no claim to the creation of these understandings, merely the gathering of the information.

It appears that the Law of Rotation is modulated by fractality and resonance in a perpetual dance involving gradients, curl, etc. This leads to the appearance of spirals and chirality in general. The result? That the living, ‘breathing’ atom-organic physical Universe has a peristalsis of behavior. The Sun does this, the weather on Earth, the beating of pulses of Pulsars and Quasars, the rise and fall of love between people, etc. all behave according to this flexion. The use of an AFW takes away the delusion of no consequence-free will, and ties everything (via Causality) to Resonance. Therefore we see that the Force begets this important reactionary action:

- ★ Resonance→Causality→Evolution (Flux or Change)
- ★ Also it is true that: Vibration→Rotation→Polarity

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/66982437/MIMS_4_21_22_White_and_Black_Spaces_in_Meditation see gif pp.10

²⁰ <https://blog.docsity.com/en/living/science-2/principles-physics-explained-educational-gifs/>

The Mind is involved - L power modulation of the A power: Eyewitness Testimony

At acupuncture college, some unfortunate male-female drama led a student of the author to betrayal and Darkness. The following semester (2011), the student (a male) was in the same class, and brought the Darkness into the classroom. The author went to the back of the room and meditated. At the end of the sequence and a 20-minute cycle of “Qi”²¹, the room ‘flexed’ and at a distance of 30 feet (10m) a picture ‘leapt’ (fell) off the wall, and hit the betrayer and Darkened one²² in his bald head, causing the class to laugh. Upon returning to his seat, T. Danio (L.Ac.) asked the author “did you just hit [redacted] in the head with the Force?” (paraphrased from memory). The author said simply, “the room did it itself.”

If there is a direct Birkeland Current or telepathic explanation, it doesn’t cover this fact. From the author’s perspective, the wave came from the left and moved right, and then as it slammed into the far end of the room, the *entire* wall structure (perhaps 25-feet in length) flexed and cracked, and there was a subtle sound to it, which the author has experienced in many meditations before and since. The picture, statistically unlikely as it was to hit the betrayer, seemed to leap off the wall and fall rapidly onto his head, disbanding the ‘evil’ feeling in the room. The author immediately returned to his seat, knowing the moment had ended. The betrayer was never in the same class again and has been “banished” (vanished) from the author’s life²³.

Attestation of events during meditation with “Angel” Ramon Careaga:

In my time in graduate school with Ramon, I had the privilege of attending his martial arts training and meditation sessions. ... On one occasion, in particular the meditation felt even more effective than before, to the point **where the energy in the room was palpable on an exceptional level during the meditation**. Immediately after opening my eyes, a picture that was hung on the wall in the room suddenly fell to the ground. We looked ... for any evidence of alternate explanations, but it felt as though the picture falling at that moment was somehow related to the energy that we had cultivated while meditating. No evidence of tampering with the picture or other physical cause for the picture falling was found.

Troy Danio L.Ac.

Mechanism Hypothesized

The main place the author found evidence for this effect came later, in clinical practice. As the author became more and more attuned to the Tao via the Changes, and the work of Liu Yiming²⁴, and increased his neuroplasticity through providing and receiving acupuncture, etc., the author began to notice the following odd effects which defy normal Newtonian mechanics and strain current Quantum mechanics, and even QED”

- The arrival at the clinic of similar type persons, back to back or same time
- The arrival on same day both via pre-schedule and walk-in of minorities and ethnic persons (of color)
- The repetitions of reported chief complains on various themes (such as shoulder pains)
- The cycles of sudden rashes of cash or check or HSA patients, versus typical credit card users
- The suddenness of the emergence of bad patients with billing issues, difficult persons to treat, and various hard cases.

²¹ Taken here to be the union of breath and aether-charge.

²² What the I Ching calls “Darkening of the Light” applied to a person (Dark Man)

²³ The details of his betrayal will be recounted in a gongfu journal at another time.

²⁴ <https://bit.ly/3SRJCjW>

- The sudden stop of patient arrival vs. sudden start, mid-way through days.
- The appearance of schedule “snafu” bubbles with patients before, and after, but in the bubble much difficulty in scheduling
- The rashes of disabled patients, or vets, or PTSD cases
- The rashes of patients with paranormal cases around the equinoxes, solstices, and Halloween, especially
- The sudden effects of storms coming while it is still high pressure and blue/clear out.
- The effects - as if a Mercury Retrograde, but more localized - during Hurricanes on approach
- The feelings of widespread dread that clears when rain starts in downpours during a treatment
- A feeling of pressure waves on dry, hot, or very cold days that penetrate the lungs, brain, or bones

Most of these require some atemporal or peritemporal mechanism, where time is involved by transcendence, or is crucial in the proximity of cases. But none of them have the appearance of normal, linearity. Instead these situations give the appearance of rotational situations of un-normalcy, or even abnormality. When all of the normal considerations such as moon phase, weather, social events, news, and solar flares are eliminated, for the most part, there remains just a sense of undulation in an underlying ME matrix. That has vortical effects upon the atomic megastructure. Including but not limited to the brain's neurons.

Conclusion

In conclusion the author wishes for plasma and quantum High-energy physicists, and VLF signal specialists to search for high-energy, low band modulations that move through structures, particularly both not only crystalline and anatomical or biological (like DNA) structures. The key is:

→ Look for these changes to happen in different types of materials seated proximally together

The search for the modulation via the L power, particularly consciousness, will not be easy, but if the above study is conducted concurrently with an fMRI, the above testimony may prove to be a guiding light in this issue.

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